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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Reducing food waste at retail stores: Sales forecasting results from Machine Learning-based software in Italy

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PAROLE CHIAVE

Inserire in questa sezione alcune parole chiave (4-6) per il contributo.

TESTO

Introduction and objective of the study

In 2020, the food waste (FW) recorded at retail stage in Europe consist of 4 million tonnes of fresh mass, that represents about the 7% of the total FW along the supply chain (Eurostat, 2023). Although retailers produce a small percentage of the total FW recorded across the food chain, their contribution to tackle the problem of FW can be crucial, since their strategies have an impact both on customer preferences and on the suppliers (Cicatiello and Franco, 2020; Cicatiello et al., 2017; Gruber et al., 2016).

Fresh fruits and vegetables (FFV) account for 54% of the total food loss and waste in Europe, making them the most wasted food products (Brautigam et al., 2014). These products also represent the main fraction, in mass, of the FW generated at the retail level (Cicatiello and Franco, 2020; Brancoli et al., 2017; Cicatiello et al., 2017; Lebersorger and Schneider, 2014).

In Italy, it has been assessed that in one Italian store in 2015 the quantity of FFV waste detected over one year was 24,035 kg, corresponding to a value of 36,372 € (Cicatiello et al., 2017). In Sweden, a study covering three stores detected 68 t of FFV wasted (Mattsson et al., 2018), while Eriksson et al. (2012) found that the rate of waste of FFV varied between 2.0% and 4.0% of the 9,605 t supplied to six stores, and that reclamations (pre-store waste) contributed to 67% of the wasted mass (Eriksson et al., 2017).

The primary drivers behind this high wastage can be attributed to the perishable nature of FFV products and the inadequate technological equipment to support their preservation (Tort et al., 2022). Retailers also face the challenge to predict the demand of products; inaccurate forecasting often results in overproduction and excessive stocks (Magalhães et al., 2021).

Despite the availability of validated technological tools to improve the sustainability of FFV supply chain, the key actors involved often lack the entrepreneurial skills necessary to understand the benefits of implementing innovations and engaging with other relevant stakeholders directly and or indirectly (Simms et al., 2020; Blasi and Cicatiello, 2019). Various authors have studied how innovations can impact the FFV supply chain and have examined the drivers and barriers to their adoption (Aramyan et al., 2021; Tort et al., 2021). Significant opportunities to improve food supply chain efficiency, traceability, transparency, and overall sustainability emerge from digital technologies. In particular, Artificial intelligence (AI), by simulating human cognitive functions including learning and reasoning, has the potential to push these changes in food systems (Onyeaka et al., 2023). Among the applications of AI, machine learning is widely studied in the field of food waste prevention to prevent overproduction, detect non-compliance causes and target products in the appropriate market, by means of forecasting, monitoring and grouping (Ciccullo et al., 2021).

The objective of the paper is to test the efficacy of a newly developed machine learning technology that provides retailers with accurate forecasts of the sales. The study aims to determine the reliability of the forecasts against real sales of FFV recorded at a panel of three retail stores in Italy. The results of the study contribute to determine whether the stores can improve the efficiency of their orders, thus avoid surplus ordering, by using the forecasts as input data for the decision making. In turn, this helps understanding and assessing the extent to which these innovations can food waste of FFV at the retail level.

Research methodology

This work is part of the H2020 project LOWINFOOD, which foresees a package of activities focused on implementing and evaluating the efficacy of innovations against losses and waste of FFV, from agricultural production up to retail.

The study has been conducted in three large retail stores (sales area >3,500 m²) located in Italy, belonging to the same retail chain, and it was specifically focused on the FFV department of the stores.

The overall research is composed of five different stages (**Figure 1**) and this study discusses the results of the first three:

1. collection of historical data from stores' records;
2. training of the forecasting algorithm with historical data;
3. analysis of the efficacy of forecasts, focused on a set of key products;
4. real-time test of the algorithm in one pilot store;
5. demonstration of the software in all the three stores for a period of three months.

Figure 1: Step of the research; the steps underlined in red are those implemented and analysed in this contribution

As for point n.1, a set of historical data was acquired from the records of the three stores, referring to the years from 2016 to 2021. Collected data included the code of the store, family, category and sub-category, product unique number, date of the sale, quantity sold, revenue, purchases, stock at the beginning and at the end of each month, data on promotions (beginning, ending, price and quantity sold), quantity of

recorded waste, surplus of products (difference between purchases and sales), inventory gap (shrink), corresponding to quantities of products that are missing in the inventory (but never sold) at the monthly recording.

In total, the dataset was composed by 2003 FFV products of which at least one sale was recorded, grouped in 109 families. The database includes 497 products which are sold by the weight (data expressed in kg and €/kg) and 1506 products which are sold by the unit (data in number of packs and €/pack). Data on all these products were used to train the algorithm.

A selection of FFV key products was made on the dataset of the year 2021. For each product, the revenue and the mass of surplus products that becomes waste were calculated, summed up for the three stores. This data includes the total quantity of waste recorded for each product and the inventory gaps for the same products (corresponding to the unrecorded waste), summed for the three stores. A percentage rate of waste was also calculated, by dividing the mass of surplus that becomes waste, for each product, and the mass of the same products supplied to the three stores.

A set of 96 key products was selected, having a turnover higher than 10,000 € and, at the same time, a rate of waste exceeding 2.5% in the year 2021. The forecasting algorithm was then trained to generate daily sales forecasts for these specific products, using a range of input variables, including sales data from the previous 30 days, day of the month, month of the year, and day of the week. Additionally, the algorithm takes into account holidays, pricing information, and promotional periods. To predict the quantities sold for each product, a machine learning approach is taken, using a multilayer perceptron model.

To assess the accuracy of the model, forecasts were generated for the entire year of 2021, and compared to actual sales data recorded on the corresponding days. The accuracy was then measured as the mean absolute error between the forecasted quantity and actual sale. In the results, the sales forecasting quantity (kg or unit) is indicated for each product studied. In the future, a reliability indicator for the forecast will also be incorporated, which is currently in development.

Basing on the results presented in this contribution, the implementation of the forecasting software in one pilot store, and then in all the three stores involved in the research, is planned. During the implementation period, the stores will feed the algorithm with the sales data every day, and they will receive the sales forecasts of the following day as an output, focusing on the key products selected.

Main results

The purchase value of all surplus quantity, across all products, is estimated on average to be 260,065 €, 189,015 € and 201,265 € annually for the three stores, resulting in waste rates of 12%, 8% and 11%, respectively. The most wasted products, among the key products considered, are oranges (rate of waste from 15% to 27%, depending on the specific product code), radicchio (21-26%), fresh tomatoes (17%), potatoes (27%) and artichokes (20%). In 2021, an analysis of recorded waste products reveals that yellow and red peppers, round eggplant, and artichokes had the highest volume of documented wastage. On the other hand, when considering the inventory gap, which represents unrecorded waste, the products with the highest volume were iceberg salad, rocket salad, and bananas. The unrecorded FFV waste across all stores constitutes approximately 88% of the total surplus. Details are presented in

Table 1.

Table 1: Details for different stores and their total surplus, surplus per year, waste rate, and unrecorded waste in euro and percentage. Based on the data from the stores that cover all the years that data were available (2016-2021)

	STORE 1	STORE 2	STORE 3	TOTAL
Total surplus that become waste (€)	1,560,392	1,134,091	1,207,592	3,902,075
Surplus per year (€)	260,065	189,015	201,265	650,346

Waste rate (%)	12.20%	8.01%	10.56%	10.16%
Unrecorded waste (€)	1,360,325	878,311	1,201,479	3,440,115
Unrecorded waste (%)¹	87.18%	77.45%	99.49%	88.16%

Table 2 presents a sample forecast of 15 arbitrary products for a single day. This information is meant to be available to the food category manager of every store for daily product ordering. The forecast serves as a decision support tool to assist them in their ordering activities. By utilising this forecast, staff members can make informed decisions regarding the quantities of products they need to order each morning.

Table 2: The table shows how the forecast information is displayed to the staff. As unit of measurement, kilogram (kg) or Number of Units (NU) have been used.

Type of product	Unit of measurement	Date	Forecast
Carrots	kg	20210524	11.35
Cabbage	kg	20210524	5.68
Zucchini	kg	20210524	56.33
Round aubergine	kg	20210524	32.27
Peppers	kg	20210524	55.53
Pack of 500 gr tomato	NU	20210524	5.23
Lettuce “romana”	kg	20210524	15.75
Red radish	kg	20210524	4.09
Cucumber	kg	20210524	45.27
Pumpkin seeds	NU	20210524	6.27

Figure 2 shows a sample forecast for a single product over the course of one month, alongside the corresponding actual outcome. To provide a benchmark for comparison, the figure also includes the data that are considered by food category managers to forecast sales in the “business-as-usual” situation: this consist of the sales data of the year before, without any further processing or formal analysis, because other variables potentially affecting the sales are evaluated upon experience.

¹ Unrecorded surplus (%) here refers to the proportion of unrecorded waste in relation to the total surplus.

Figure 2: This figure compares the actual outcome of quantity sold for a specific product, with two different forecasting models.

To assess the accuracy of the forecasting model, the model was tested on data from 2021, which was not included in the model’s training data. The accuracy is measured as the mean absolute error of the forecast and expressed as a percentage of total sales for the same period. The results for five example products can be seen in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: The accuracy of our forecasting model for five example products in one store during 2021, compared to the model currently employed by the stores, where the quantity sold is assumed to be the same as last year on the same date.

Table 3 displays the overall performance and reliability of our model compared to the model that is currently used by the stores. The table compares a sample of 15 products out of the 96. The mean average error is found to be approximately twice as large for the stores' current model compared to the new model in development.

Table 3: Comparison of a sample of 15 products from the suggested 96. Our selection criteria focused on choosing products with a substantial amount of data available. Specifically, we aimed to include products where the number of data points for our model and the current model were approximately equal. To assess the reliability of the models, we utilise the MAE/AVERGAE SALE measure. This metric is based on the quantities sold for each product and provides insight into the accuracy and performance of the forecasting models. As unit of measurement, kilogram (Kg) or Number of Units (NU) have been used.

Product no	Unit of measurement	Our Model		Current Model	
		MAE	Data points	MAE	Data points
Salad “trocadero / cappuccina”	kg	28.8%	355	53.3%	344
Green tomato	kg	30.1%	289	82.1%	301
Pack of 1.5 kg of golden apple	NU	50.0%	226	168.2%	270
Pack of 80 gr of parsley	NU	30.9%	357	47.4%	347
Lettuce “romana”	kg	26.1%	355	48.1%	343
Pack of 125 gr of argula	NU	23.9%	354	50.5%	343
Salad “gentilina”	kg	32.8%	141	73.9%	170
Red radicchio	kg	30.4%	354	64.5%	341
Black savoy cabbage	kg	36.3%	347	86.5%	321
Pack of 400 gr of salad “iceberg”	NU	30.5%	284	54.6%	303
Classic mixed salad	NU	41.9%	355	58.1%	344
Squash blossom	Nu	45.3%	344	76.4%	328
Yellow winter melon	kg	38.9%	354	61.5%	339
Pineapple	kg	52.0%	218	61.4%	199
Escarole	kg	42.2%	244	84.1%	288
AVERAGE		36.0%		71.4%	

Discussion and conclusions

Monitoring sales and waste data at retail stores is crucial to inform strategies to reduce food waste. In this study, we collected very detailed and informative data about sales, promotions and waste at three Italian retail stores, at the single product level for the food category of fruits and vegetables. One first evidence we found from these stores is the incidence of unrecorded food waste in the FFV product category. Previous evidence estimated the rate of unrecorded waste around 1/3 of total food waste (Eriksson et al., 2012; Cicatiello et al., 2020). Instead, the inventory gaps for FFV products at these stores reveal a much greater incidence of unrecorded food waste. This suggests that, especially in the FFV departments of retail stores, the procedures for waste monitoring shall still be improved.

Concerning the results of the forecasting software, they show that considerable improvements are possible in the information which is available to food category managers to place the orders. The overall performance of the new forecast model shows a substantial improvement with respect to the business-as-usual, reducing the error by approximately 50% compared to the current model in use. However, it is important to note that the forecasts generated by the model should not be directly considered as ordering suggestions. When placing orders, it may be advisable for the stores to incorporate a safety margin to prevent potential shortages. Additionally, they should consider the remaining stock from previous days to optimize their ordering decisions. Conducting a real test in an operational environment will be crucial to evaluate the extent to which the forecasts are truly trusted and utilised in the ordering process.

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